

Halogenation. Part X. Iodination of Xylenes and Mono-iodoxylenes.

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In the present communication we have described the iodination of the three xylenes and their mono-iodo derivatives (*cf.* Varma and others, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 291, 342). The mono-iodo-xylenes can be prepared in better yields in presence of nitro-sulphonic acid mixture containing about 50% fuming nitric acid. The di-iodo derivative can be obtained both by the iodination of the respective xylenes themselves and the mono-iodo-xylenes. The di-iodo-derivatives of *o*- and *p*-xylenes have been prepared for the first time and their constitution has been suggested only from analogy with the corresponding chloro and bromo compounds as 4:5-di-iodo-*o*-xylene and 2:5-di-iodo-*p*-xylene.

EXPERIMENTAL.

4-Iodo-o-xylene.—A mixture of *o*-xylene (15 c.c.), powdered iodine (15 g.) and acetic acid (10 c.c.) was heated on a sand bath in a flask with a reflux condenser and a mixture of fuming nitric and nitro-sulphonic acids (7 c.c.) was added to it drop by drop in about 10 minutes and the heating continued for about 20 minutes more. The product was washed free of iodine by 5% sodium hydroxide solution and steam distilled. The pinkish oil was separated, dried over fused calcium chloride and distilled. The fraction distilling between 228-35° was found to be almost pure 4-iodo-*o*-xylene (21 g.) and the residue in the flask contained traces of nitro-*o*-xylene.

m-Xylene and *p*-xylene under foregoing treatment yielded 4-iodo-*m*-xylene (74%) and 2-iodo-*p*-xylene (65%) respectively. In both cases nitroxylene was also obtained in very small quantity.

4:5-Di-iodo-o-xylene—(i) From *o*-xylene—To a mixture of *o*-xylene (10 c.c.), iodine (18 g.) and acetic acid (20 c.c.) in a flask heated on a sand bath, nitro-sulphonic acid mixture (10 c.c.) was added drop by drop in about half an hour and the reaction mixture heated further for about 5.5 hours. The flask was then cooled, the product washed with a dilute solution of sodium hydroxide till free from iodine, dried over fused calcium chloride

and then cooled in a freezing mixture of ice and salt at about -20° when plate like crystals separated out. It was filtered in the cold and was recrystallised first from carbon tetrachloride and then from ether, m.p. 73° . (Found: 1, 68.89 $C_8H_8I_2$ requires 1, 70.93 per cent). It is easily soluble in carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, carbon disulphide, benzene and ether; very sparingly soluble in cold absolute alcohol; slightly soluble in glacial acetic acid in the cold but more on warming.

(ii) From 4-iodo-*o*-xylene.—To a mixture of 4-iodo-*o*-xylene (6 c.c.), iodine (7 g.), acetic acid (5 c.c.) and carbon tetrachloride (5 c.c.) heated on a sand bath to about 170° , nitro-sulphonic acid mixture (5.5 c.c.) was added in about 15 minutes and the heating continued for about 1.5 hours more, the temperature of the bath being maintained at about 235° . The reaction product was then subjected to the same treatment as in the preceding experiment, yield 6.2 g.

4:6-di-iodo-*m*-xylene (m.p. 72°) can be obtained from *m*-xylene or from 4-iodo-*m*-xylene in a similar manner. This compound is identical with the 4:6-di-iodo-*m*-xylene prepared by Hammerich (*Ber.*, 1890, 23, 1635) and Tohl (*Ber.*, 1893, 26, 1105).

2:5-Di-iodo-*p*-xylene (i) From *p*-xylene.—To *p*-xylene (10 c.c.), iodine (20 g.), and acetic acid (15 c.c.) heated on a sand bath, nitrosulphonic acid mixture (12 c.c.) was added in proportions of 2 c.c. at a time in about an hour. The flask with its contents was further heated to about 220° for about 5 hours. The solid product was separated as described before, m.p. 104° . (Found: I, 69.74. $C_8H_8I_2$ requires I, 70.93 per cent). The solubility is the same as in the case of 4:5-di-iodo-*o*-xylene.

(ii) From 2-iodo-*p*-xylene.—To 2-iodo-*p*-xylene (10 c.c.), powdered iodine (12 g.) and acetic acid (10 c.c.) in a flask heated on a sand bath, nitrosulphonic acid mixture (6 c.c.) was added drop by drop in about half an hour and the heating continued for about 2.5 hours. The product was worked up as described in the previous experiments, yield 12.3 g.

This compound has further been obtained by putting together 2-iodo-*p*-xylene (5 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (14 c.c.) in a test tube and allowing them to stand for 9 weeks. Crystals of the di-iodo derivative (1.8 g.) separated out.